

EMBEDMENT OF GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

The present article is devoted to investigation of different games for teaching English as foreign language. The author points the main advantages of using games in teaching process.

Key words: games, advantages, real context, authentic atmosphere, communicative skills, perception.

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Language learning is hard work ... Effort is required at every moment and must be maintained over a long period of time. Games help and encourage many learners to sustain their interest and work. Games also help the teacher to create contexts in which the language is useful and meaningful. The learners want to take part and in order to do so must understand what others are saying or have written, and they must speak or write in order to express their own point of view or give information.

There is a common perception that all learning should be serious and solemn in nature, and that if one is having fun and there is hilarity and laughter, then it is not really learning. This is a misconception. It is possible to learn a language as well as enjoy oneself at the same time. One of the best ways of doing this is through games. Language learning is an important task which can sometimes be frustrating. Constant effort is required to understand, produce and manipulate the target language. Well-chosen games are invaluable as they give students a break and at the same time allow students to practice language skills. Games are highly motivating since they are amusing and at the same time challenging. Furthermore, they employ meaningful and useful language in real contexts. They also encourage and increase cooperation. Games are highly motivating because they are amusing and interesting. They can be used to give practice in all language skills and be used to practice many types of communication [3, p.35].

Games during lesson have great educational value. Games should be treated as central not peripheral to the foreign language teaching program. There are many advantages of using games: they are highly motivating and entertaining and they can give shy students more opportunity to express their opinions and feelings. They also enable learners to acquire new experiences within a foreign language which are not always possible during a typical lesson [2, p.43].

Games can make the students more focus in learning, because they do not feel that they are forced to learn.

Games can lower anxiety, thus making the acquisition of input more likely [4, p.440]. They are highly motivating and entertaining, and they can give shy students more opportunity to express their opinion and feelings. They also enable learners to acquire new experiences within a foreign language which are not always possible during a typical lesson. Games can be media that will give many advantages for teacher and the students either.

The useful of games are attract the student to learn English because it is fun and make them want to have experiment, discover and interact with their environment:

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Even shy students can participate positively.

Make your classroom a lively place through the use of attractive wall displays, displays of pupils' work, etc. language classroom is noisy with the language (English) is good because it will make the classroom more alive in English (practice).

Motivate pupils to want to learn English by using interesting and enjoyable learning activities. E.g., project work, games, drama. It means learning by playing.

Create warm and happy atmosphere where teacher and pupil enjoy working together. Teacher arranges good atmosphere in classroom and make the students interested [5].

Help pupils to develop personal reasons for learning English. For example, by encouraging out-of-school class activities, e.g. pen friends, project, reading story books.

Many experienced textbook and methodology manuals writers have argued that games are not just time-filling activities but have a great educational value. Most language games make learners use the language instead of thinking about learning the correct forms. Games should be treated as central not peripheral to the foreign language teaching program. Games to be fun but warns against overlooking their pedagogical value, particularly in foreign language teaching [1, p.67].

In the easy, relaxed atmosphere which is created by using games, students remember things faster and better. Many teachers are enthusiastic about using games as "a teaching device," yet they often perceive games as mere time-fillers, "a break from the monotony of drilling" or frivolous activities. Many teachers often overlook the fact that in a relaxed atmosphere, real learning takes place, and students use the language they have been exposed to and have practiced earlier.

Games encourage, entertain, teach, and promote fluency. If not for any of these reasons, they should be used just because they help students see beauty in a foreign language and not just problems that at times seem overwhelming.

Games have been shown to have advantages and effectiveness in learning vocabulary in various ways. First, games bring in relaxation and fun for students, thus help them learn and retain new words more easily. Second, games usually involve friendly competition and they keep learners interested. These create the motivation for learners of English to get involved and participate actively in the learning activities. Third, vocabulary games bring real world context into the classroom, and enhance students' use of English in a flexible, communicative way.

Therefore, the role of games in teaching and learning vocabulary cannot be denied. However, in order to achieve the most from vocabulary games, it is essential that suitable games are chosen. Whenever a game is to be conducted, the number of students, proficiency level, cultural context, timing, learning topic, and the classroom settings are factors that should be taken into account.

For example, learning vocabulary through games is one effective and interesting way that can be applied in any classrooms. The results of this research suggest that games are used not only for mere fun, but more importantly, for the useful practice and review of language lessons, thus leading toward the goal of improving learners' communicative competence.

There are many advantages of using games in the classroom:

1. Games are a welcome break from the usual routine of the language class.
2. They are motivating and challenging.
3. Learning a language requires a great deal of effort. Games help students to make and sustain the effort of learning.
4. Games provide language practice in the various skills- speaking, writing, listening and reading.
5. They encourage students to interact and communicate.
6. They create a meaningful context for language use.

Thus, games can be a very worthwhile teaching element. A successful game is successful because for the reason that it is based on specific time allocation, it has clear relevance to the material, there is appropriateness to all members of the class, and ultimately, the enjoyment of the learners is increased through their actively engaging with the language.

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